

IN VITRO SHORT-TIME TESTING METHOD FOR EVALUATING THE LONG-TIME CORROSION FATIGUE STRENGTH OF BIOMEDICAL MAGNESIUM ALLOYS

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Biodegradable magnesium alloys show promise in surgical disciplines due to their low corrosion resistance. This characteristic, typically undesirable in technical applications, becomes advantageous for medical implants as it allows gradual degradation in the presence of body fluids and enables support during bone healing for a defined period, eliminating the need for a second surgery for removal. To prevent early implant failure, precise knowledge of the degradation behaviour over several months and its impact on mechanical stability is crucial. Therefore, for the alloy WE43, with and without plasma electrolytic oxidation modification, an in vitro short-time testing method was developed to accelerate degradation through polarisation without altering the existing mechanism. To quantify the influence of polarisation on the service life and thus to validate the short-time testing method, corrosion fatigue tests were carried out with and without polarisation. Results indicate that qualitative replication of the corrosion rate is possible through the testing method, leading to significant time savings. However, due to altered degradation morphology with increased pitting susceptibility and a resulting reduction in corrosion fatigue strength, this method should be considered a worst-case estimation, aiding in identifying unsuitable Mg-based biomaterials before advancing to further preclinical studies.

Keywords: Biodegradable implants, Magnesium alloys, Corrosion fatigue, Short-time testing method

INTRODUCTION

Research in surgical fields is increasingly focused on biodegradable magnesium (Mg) implants for treating bone defects. Beyond being biodegradable, magnesium possesses mechanical properties comparable to human cortical bone, reducing the risk of bone resorption due to stress shielding. Its inherent degradability allows temporary support during the healing of the weakened bone, preventing the need for a subsequent removal surgery (Chen et al. [1], Staiger et al. [2]). When exposed to human body fluids, magnesium degrades under the formation of magnesium hydroxide and hydrogen gas. According to Song and Atrens [3], this degradation (used analogously to corrosion) process can be divided into three stages. Initially, magnesium oxidises into a single positively charged Mg^+ ion (Equation 1), subsequently further oxidising into a twice positively charged Mg^{2+} ion (Equation 2), resulting in the formation of hydrogen gas and hydroxide ions. Both reactions are balanced by Equation 3 and summarised in Equation 4, while the products are specified in Equation 5 [3].

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Aside from the corrosion rate (reaction rate), the degradation morphology plays a crucial role in ensuring the stability of the implant and, consequently, the duration of its functional phase. To guarantee patient safety during this phase, it is essential to reliably determine both the corrosion rate and morphology (Raman et al. [4]). However, performing corresponding in vitro tests reproducing in vivo corrosion is time- and cost-consuming due to extended implantation periods (Hou et al. [5]). The commonly used Mg alloys exhibit degradation behaviour changing over time, necessitating the capability to perform time-dependent evaluations. This specific behaviour arises from the development of degradation layers that, depending on their composition, partially protect the underlying substrate material. Additionally, micro-galvanic corrosion occurs, leading to pitting corrosion and an associated increase in corrosion rate (Öcal et al. [6], Ascencio et al. [7]). In contrast to electrochemical short-time techniques such as potentiodynamic polarisation and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, the immersion test enables a time-dependent evaluation and is, therefore, suitable for long-time assessment of corrosion behaviour (Zheng et al. [8]). As per Equation 4, it is possible to determine the corrosion rate by measuring the volume of hydrogen gas produced during this reaction ([6], Nidadavolu et al. [9]). In most applications, Mg implants are not subjected solely to corrosion but superimposed with the effects of cyclic mechanical stress. In this context, the corrosion fatigue behaviour of Mg alloys in body-like environments is much discussed ([4], Maier et al. [10]) and is attributed to different mechanisms: Stress concentrations and standard potential differences between the phases favour local corrosive attack (including pitting) and plastic deformation so that both effects influence and reinforce each other (Bian et al. [11]). Through the occurrence of extrusions and intrusions during cyclic loading and the mismatch in mechanical properties between the substrate material and the degradation layer, the layer is disrupted locally, leading to exposure and then again to localised corrosion of the substrate material (Gu et al. [12], Han et al. [13]). For these mechanisms, a drastic reduction in fatigue strength was found using the AZ series ([12], Raman and Harandi [14]). Further studies on WE43, ZX10, pure Mg, Mg1Ca, and Mg2Zn0.2Ca confirm these mechanisms ([11,12], Jafari et al. [15]). As an additional mechanism, occurring simultaneously and interacting with the previously mentioned mechanisms, other studies mention hydrogen embrittlement at the crack tip and, thus, accelerated crack propagation [15]. All studies describe local corrosion effects, promoting crack initiation and leading to premature failure (Liu et al. [16], Zhao et al. [17]). The performance of corrosion fatigue tests, which are costly anyway, with a testing time corresponding to the application, would lead to an enormous expenditure of time and cost. To reduce these, an approach is to utilise short-time testing methods, e.g. accelerating the degradation process. One method involves the application of an anodic potential, resulting in an increased anodic current, which accelerates the formation of positively charged Mg^{x+} ions (Equation 1 and 2) and product formation (Equation 4 and 5). Various studies have demonstrated that the hydrogen evolution rate (HER) remains constant applying a constant current density (Shi et al. [18], Shi et al. [(19)], Huang et al. [20]). Furthermore, the HER and the mass loss correlate linearly [18,19], primarily attributed to an increase in hydrogen evolution on more noble impurities or phases

(Thomas et al. [21]). Jafari et al. [22] attributed the decrease in corrosion fatigue properties under anodic polarisation to the increased anodic dissolution in combination with a higher susceptibility to pitting and increased hydrogen evolution. However, the present study makes use of the correlation between the current density, HER, and mass loss to design a method for simulating the long-time degradation process. The validation and in-depth investigation are carried out by superimposing a cyclic loading to determine the respective corrosion fatigue strengths. This method enables a time-efficient evaluation of long-time immersion behaviour and corresponding mechanical stability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The used Mg alloy WE43 (Meotec, Aachen, Germany) exhibits an elemental composition containing 1.4-4.2% Y, 2.5-3.5% Nd, less than 1% of Al, Fe, Cu, Ni, Mn, Zn, Zr, and balance Mg (in wt.%). Cylindrical specimens with a gauge length of 9 mm and an initial diameter of 4 mm were machined from the raw material, which was initially chill-casted and extruded. Additionally, a second material variant featured a surface modification with plasma electrolytic oxidation (PEO, Kermasorb[®], Meotec, Aachen, Germany). To ensure a defined and area-specific corrosion process, an anti-corrosion lacquer was applied outside the gauge length of the specimens.

The raw material possesses a fine microstructure characterised by a considerable number of intermetallic precipitates (Figure 1). These are evenly distributed and vary in size, ranging from ca. 50 nm to several micrometres. They exhibit diverse shapes, including round, rod-shaped, and branched forms, with no discernible preference in orientation in the cross-section. However, in the longitudinal-section, these precipitates appear elongated and parallel to the extrusion direction as a consequence of the process temperatures and deformations (Zeng et al. [23]). The precipitates can be classified into yttrium-rich (such as MgY, Mg₁₄Y₅, Mg₂₄Y₅), neodymium-rich (including Mg₄₁Nd₅, Mg₁₂Nd), and zirconium-rich precipitates (Esmaily et al. [24], Xiang et al. [25]). On the other hand, the PEO-layer (Figure 2) has a thickness of approx. 25 ± 4 µm and the typical high porosity, with variations in shapes, sizes, and positions of pores, along with brittleness evident in the form of cracks (Darband et al. [26]). In terms of mechanical stability, the presence of large, branched pores that connect to the substrate material is considered a critical factor.

Qualitative contact potential differences and chemical properties of the precipitates were characterised using correlative scanning electron and atomic force microscopy (AFM). Contact potential mapping in the longitudinal-section was acquired using frequency modulated Kelvin probe force microscopy (FM-KPFM) with heterodyne detection (Sugawara et al. [27]). Topography was measured in contact in first pass and KPFM signal with a constant offset in second pass. For AFM investigations piezo based Litescope 2.0 (NenoVision, Brno-Medlány, Czech Republic) mounted with a conductive probe with a 50 nm radius platinum coated tip and first resonance frequency of 48.2 kHz together with an MFLI lock-in amplifier (Zurich Instruments, Zurich, Switzerland) were used. With the setup described a DC bias V_{DC} is applied in the second pass by the lock-in amplifier to nullify the modulation with inverse contrast to the surface's work function. Therefore, in Figure 1 a more negative V_{DC} means higher, nobler local potential. AFM was mounted inside a Crossbeam XB 550 L (Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) FIB-SEM to enable correlative EDS investigation of the region of interest. To prevent contamination from the electron beam, SEM analyses were performed after AFM. For EDS an acceleration voltage of 6 kV was chosen. EDS mappings allow to differentiate between neodymium-, yttrium-, and zirconium-rich precipitates. In topography mapping (Figure 1 c)) the large inclusion is not visible, though in V_{DC} mapping (b)), it appears more noble than the surrounding Mg matrix. This is in general visible for the neodymium-rich and magnesium-depleted zones. The very small, and according to the topography, high inclusion

to the lower right of the large inclusion has brighter secondary electron contrast similar to the yttrium- and zirconium-rich precipitate to the very right of the SEM image. Possibly due to its small size of 150 nm, it was not detected in EDS, but in KPFM, it is visible as the most noble region.

FIGURE 1 Longitudinal-section of WE43 viewed under a) scanning electron microscope (SEM), b) Kelvin probe force microscope (KPFM), c) topography, and as EDS mappings of d) magnesium, e) neodymium, f) yttrium, and g) zirconium.

FIGURE 2 Plasma electrolytic oxidation (PEO) layer: a) top view, b) cross-section [30].

Corrosion without cyclic mechanical stress

Data from a previously published study (Hartjen et al. [28]) was utilised to calculate the corrosion rates $\dot{m}_{\text{corr}}$ using Equation 4. In the course of three-week ($t_{\text{OCP}} = 504$ h) immersion tests conducted at open circuit potential (OCP), the specific hydrogen volume $V_{\text{H}_2, \text{spec}}$ was measured for both material variants. The results were divided into three periods, each characterised by an approx. constant hydrogen evolution rate (HER) and, consequently, a constant corrosion rate, as detailed in Table 1. The preliminary research focused on the correlation between the corrosion rate and the current density i (using galvanostatic polarisation (GSP)) for embedded WE43 specimens. For this specimen

type, only the cross-sectional area was taken into account, designating it as a two-dimensional (2D) case. As a result of these investigations, Equation 6 was derived, establishing a relationship between the current density and the corrosion rate (Wegner and Walther [29]). Both exponents are material- and geometry-dependent. For embedded WE43 specimens and PEO-modified cylindrical specimens, $A_1 = 3.139$ and $A_2 = 1.094$ are assumed. For WE43 cylindrical specimens, the slope A_2 of the function does not change, whereas the second exponent changes to $A_1 = 3.372$. Building on these relationships, this research aims to simulate the three-week immersion tests by utilising GSP to achieve an identical mass loss ($m_{corr} = \dot{m}_{corr} \times t \rightarrow \dot{m}_{corr,OCP} \times t_{OCP} = \dot{m}_{corr,GSP} \times t_{GSP}$) in a shortened period t_{GSP} comparable to the initial immersion time t_{OCP} . Based on this assumption, Equation 7 was established, enabling the calculation of the current density required for a specified corrosion rate.

TABLE 1 Design of immersion tests with galvanostatic polarisation on WE43 (PEO) [28-30].

Material	Corrosion rate $\dot{m}_{corr}$ ($10^3 \text{ mg cm}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$)	Time interval (h)		Current density i (mA cm^{-2})
		t_{OCP}	t_{GSP}	
WE43	0.21	0-114.4	0-16.3	0.64
	0.12	114.4-241.5	16.3-34.5	0.38
	0.18	241.5-504.0	34.5-72.0	0.57
WE43 PEO	0.15	0-111.6	0-15.9	0.77
	0.07	111.6-268.5	15.9-38.4	0.41
	0.09	268.5-504.0	38.4-72.0	0.51

$$\dot{m}_{corr} = 10^{A_1} \times i^{A_2} \tag{6}$$

$$i = \sqrt[A_2]{\dot{m}_{corr,OCP} \times \frac{t_{OCP}}{t_{GSP}} \times 10^{A_1}} \tag{7}$$

Galvanostatic polarisation

The test setup allowed the application of GSP and the measurement of the resulting hydrogen volume. A corrosion cell was supplied with a 0.9% NaCl solution (36.5 °C), controlled by a thermostat and a peristaltic pump. Within the corrosion cell, a three-electrode system enabled the usage of GSP. The specimen served as working electrode, a graphite rod functioned as counter electrode, and an Ag/AgCl electrode with a Haber-Luggin capillary served as reference electrode. The polarisation was regulated using a PCI4300 potentiostat (Gamry Instruments, Warminster, PA, USA). To detect changes in the liquid level and, consequently, the hydrogen gas produced, a eudiometer was employed. The objective was to replicate the degradation observed in the three-week immersion tests within a shortened period of three days. Utilising Equation 7, the initial corrosion rates, and a factor of 7 ($t_{OCP}/t_{GSP} = 21/3$), the current densities were calculated (Table 1). The tests were performed intermittently, with pauses to change the electrolyte after every 24-hour interval.

Micro-computed tomography

μ -computed tomography (μ CT) scans of the gauge length were conducted to assess the macroscopic degradation morphology. The scans were performed utilising an X TH 160 μ CT system (Nikon,

Tokyo, Japan) featuring a maximum accelerating voltage of 160 kV. Specific scanning parameters included a beam energy of 105 kV, a beam current of 55 μA , a power output of 5.8 W, an exposure time between 354 and 500 ms, and a resolution of 5 μm . The analysis of the reconstructed volumes was carried out using VGStudio Max 2.2 software (Volume Graphics, Heidelberg, Germany).

Fatigue testing

Multiple amplitude tests (MAT) were performed after immersion at OCP and under GSP using an ElectroPuls E3000 electro-mechanical testing system (Instron, Norwood, MA, USA) to assess the mechanical stability by estimating the residual fatigue strength. Beginning at an initial stress amplitude of $\sigma_{a,\text{start}} = 10 \text{ MPa}$, the stress amplitude was continuously increased with a rate of $d\sigma_a/dN = 10 \text{ MPa}/10^4$ under a frequency of $f = 10 \text{ Hz}$ and a stress ratio of $R = -1$. An extensometer was utilised for instrumentation to analyse the stress-strain hysteresis, including plastic strain amplitude $\varepsilon_{a,p}$, and loss energy density w_L , while a thermal camera was employed to monitor temperature changes. The uncorroded reference specimens were subjected to an initial stress amplitude of $\sigma_{a,\text{start}} = 50 \text{ MPa}$.

Constant amplitude tests (CAT) were performed on uncorroded specimens as well on the electro-mechanical testing system and are used to determine the actual fatigue and corrosion fatigue strengths at OCP and under GSP, respectively, at a maximum number of cycles of $N_{\text{limit}} = 2 \times 10^6$. The tests at OCP were performed analogously to the preliminary work [28] in a modified minimum essential medium (mMEM) and with an immersion time of 2 and 4 days. The corrosion fatigue tests under GSP were conducted analogously to the immersion tests (see above) in 0.9% NaCl solution (36.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and with an immersion time of 1, 2, and 3 days, respectively. The testing frequencies varied and resulted from the constant N_{limit} and the respective immersion time; the CAT in air were carried out at $f = 10 \text{ Hz}$. In other studies, a significant influence of corrosion was observed for comparable frequencies in corrosion fatigue tests [11,12,15]. The stress ratio was $R = -1$ for all testing strategies. Due to the high number of parameters, only one test is carried out for each parameter combination in both testing series (MAT, CAT).

RESULTS

Parts of the results have already been published in (Wegner et al. [30]).

In Figure 3 a), the results of the immersion tests under galvanostatic polarisation (GSP) are presented, with the specific hydrogen volume $V_{\text{H}_2,\text{spec}}$ plotted against the normalised immersion time t/t_{max} . The lines represent the arithmetic means of the actual values and target values (based on Table 1). In qualitative terms, the curves for both material variants exhibit similarities. At the start of each day ($t/t_{\text{max}} = \{0; 0.33; 0.67\}$), is an initial progressive trend that transitions into a linear one. Altering the current density results in changes in the hydrogen evolution rate (HER). In quantitative terms, WE43 achieves higher values than its PEO-modified counterpart throughout the immersion period. By comparing target and actual values, it becomes apparent that while the qualitative trends are similar, there are quantitative differences, particularly for WE43. These differences increase with the immersion time. For evaluation of the short-time testing method, Figure 3 b) illustrates the corrosion rate $\dot{m}_{\text{corr}}$ plotted against the current density i . Gray points represent data from previous tests conducted on embedded WE43 specimens (two-dimensional (2D)) [29], along with the linear fits used to design the current series of tests. The coloured data points correspond to tests conducted on the three-dimensional (3D) cylindrical specimens. Most data points agree with the respective

calculation functions for both material variants. The existing deviations for WE43 tend to lower corrosion rates, whereas the PEO-modified variant tends to higher corrosion rates, especially for longer immersion times.

FIGURE 3 Results of immersion tests of WE43 (PEO): a) mean hydrogen evolution at open circuit potential (OCP) and with galvanostatic polarisation (GSP); b) corrosion rates calculated via hydrogen evolution rate (HER) for different current densities [30].

FIGURE 4 μ CT images after immersion at open circuit potential (OCP): a) WE43, 2 weeks, b) PEO, 2 weeks, c) WE43, 3 weeks; after immersion under galvanostatic polarisation (GSP): d) WE43, 1 day, e) PEO, 1 day, f) WE43, 1 day. a)-e) Cross-section, f) longitudinal-section.

Figure 4 provides exemplary μ CT images of the macroscopic corrosion morphologies. Images a)–c) show corrosion conditions at OCP, while images d)–f) show conditions after GSP. In the case of WE43 without polarisation, as seen in image a), a predominantly uniform corrosive attack is observed. However, in individual cases, deep, branched pitting can be recognised (image c)). In contrast, the PEO-modified specimens (image b)) exhibit no apparent localised corrosion, displaying only a slight reduction in layer thickness and minimal damage within the layer. Under the influence of polarisation, all specimens, irrespective of their surface condition, exhibit enhanced local corrosion. In the longitudinal-section (image f)), the pitting is aligned parallel to the extrusion

direction. Both in longitudinal- and cross-section, it becomes evident that the pitting extends along the accumulation of alloying elements, which appear as lighter areas.

As an example, in Figure 5, the results of a multiple amplitude test (MAT) conducted on the substrate material WE43 in its initial condition are presented. The plotted data includes the stress amplitude σ_a as the controlled variable with the loss energy density w_L exemplary as the measured variable, plotted against the number of cycles N . To evaluate the measured variable, according to Ebel-Wolf et al. [34], its mathematical regression and its derivation are formed. For simplification, the first approx. constant range and the abrupt increase before fracture are excluded. The transition from the linear to the exponential range of the derivation is used to estimate the fatigue strength ($N_{\text{limit}} = 2 \times 10^6$) at 167 MPa, which is, therefore, below the yield strength of at least 221 MPa.

FIGURE 5 Development of the loss energy density, the mathematical regression, and its derivation in a multiple amplitude test (MAT) for WE43 (initial condition) with fatigue strength estimation.

FIGURE 6 a) Multiple amplitude test (MAT) after immersion at open circuit potential (OCP) and under galvanostatic polarisation (GSP), b) (corrosion) fatigue strength for different immersion times at OCP and under GSP, WE43 (PEO).

The summary of the estimated fatigue and residual fatigue strengths is given in Figure 6 a). In the initial condition, the estimated fatigue strength of the unmodified specimens is slightly higher than that of the PEO-modified specimens, with values of 173.8 MPa and 169.2 MPa, respectively. As the immersion time at OCP increases, the residual fatigue strength of both materials decreases, with lower values estimated for WE43. For GSP, there is a substantial decrease in the estimated residual fatigue strength after just one day of immersion, followed by a gradual decline on day 2 and 3. Notably, differences between both material variants become less pronounced. The estimated fatigue strengths of the testing strategy employing GSP are significantly lower than those observed in the tests conducted at OCP. The estimations and interrelations made through MAT are confirmed by the fatigue and corrosion fatigue strengths plotted in Figure 6 b) against the immersion time. For the reference condition in air at room temperature ($t_{OCP} = 0$ days), the fatigue strength of the substrate material WE43 ($\sigma_{a,fs} = 180$ MPa) determined by constant amplitude tests (CAT) is slightly above that of the PEO-modified variant (175 MPa). For an immersion time of $t_{OCP} = 2$ days, the corrosion fatigue strengths of both variants correspond (140 MPa), whereas the corrosion fatigue strength of the substrate material decreases to a greater extent with increasing immersion time. However, there is a linear relationship between the (corrosion) fatigue strength and the immersion time for WE43, which, when extrapolated, is significantly higher than the corrosion fatigue strength under GSP for $t_{GSP} = 1$ day (simulating $t_{OCP} = 7$ days). The residual fatigue strengths estimated by MAT tend to lie above the (corrosion) fatigue strengths determined by CAT.

DISCUSSION

The immersion tests performed under galvanostatic polarisation (GSP) reveal that the specific hydrogen volume follows a linear course for a constant current density. The initial progressive trend at the start of each testing day is explained by the formation of hydrogen gas bubbles on the surface, only detaching after reaching a critical size (Yang et al. [31]). Based on prior investigations [29] and literature [18,19], it is established that the corrosion rate is proportional to the current density. Consequently, any alteration in current density leads to a change in the hydrogen evolution rate (HER). The PEO-modified variant deviates slightly from the target values and only with increasing immersion time (+17%), whereas the substrate material is below the target values and achieves a maximum deviation of -21%. The lower hydrogen volumes observed for PEO-modified specimens correlate with the lower targeted corrosion rates (Table 1). Thus, these tests indicate that qualitative control of HER is achievable through the application of polarisation. The calculated corrosion rates (Figure 3 b)) agree mainly with the calculation function for WE43. The existing deviations tend towards lower values so that the lower hydrogen volume during the immersion tests is explained. For the PEO-modified variant, only the corrosion rates for longer immersion times deviate from the corresponding calculation function, the other values coincide with it. The deviation to higher corrosion rates correlates with the enhanced HER and the resulting deviation from the target values. In general, based on the hydrogen evolution and the corrosion rates for both material variants, a good agreement with the target values and, thus, a first validation of the short-time method is assumed.

Nevertheless, for WE43 with and without PEO-modification, the resulting degradation morphologies differ from the immersion tests at open circuit potential (OCP, Figure 4). Hereby, the longitudinal-section of the microstructure predominantly influences the material behaviour. In this context, elongated precipitates with a higher contact potential (Figure 1 b)) are present due to the extrusion process, favouring pitting corrosion. Under immersion tests performed at OCP, the occurrence of pitting corrosion is subjected to a statistical probability [7] and is typically observed only for individual specimens, particularly after extended immersion times. However, due to GSP,

this effect is intensified [21], leading to pronounced pitting corrosion along the precipitates, which is observable for all specimens. The protective effects of the PEO-layer, which leads to lower corrosion rates, a more uniform corrosion morphology, and higher residual fatigue strengths at OCP, become negligible under polarisation. Consequently, the testing methodology does not apply to the PEO-modified material. For the substrate material WE43, GSP intensifies the existing pitting tendency on nobler precipitates, making the short-time testing method a worst-case estimation.

Differences in fatigue behaviour between pre-corroded specimens after immersion at OCP and under GSP and between the corrosion fatigue tests with and without GSP arise due to the altered degradation mechanisms. Based on previous studies (Klein et al. [32]), the first exponential increase in a multiple amplitude test (MAT) can be used to estimate the (residual) fatigue strength. Intensive pre-corrosion under polarisation results in, as described before, pitting corrosion and significant material embrittlement, and, thus, in a drastic decrease in estimated residual fatigue strength after just one day of immersion for both material variants. The gradual decrease on day 2 and 3 suggests that the number and size of pitting may have reached a critical point after the initial day and change minimally afterward. This effect is observed for both material variants, and despite their different corrosion rates, there are hardly any discernible differences in residual fatigue strength. These results were used to choose the stress amplitudes of the corrosion fatigue tests with and without polarisation. For the initial condition (i.e., without corrosion), PEO-modification leads to slightly lower fatigue strengths compared to the substrate material. This is attributed to the porous and brittle nature of the oxide ceramic layer, which promotes premature crack initiation (Němcová et al. [33]). Given the higher corrosion rates at OCP for the substrate material WE43 (Table 1), the corrosion fatigue strengths decrease significantly over time compared to the PEO-modified variant. Additionally, the modification leads to a more uniform corrosion morphology (Figure 4 b)), favouring increased corrosion fatigue strength. For an immersion time of 2 days, the corrosion fatigue strengths are equal so that the two effects of crack initiation within the PEO-layer and the increased corrosion resistance seem to compensate each other. With a further extension of the immersion time, the increased corrosion resistance of the modification dominates. In general, the (corrosion) fatigue strengths were successfully estimated by MAT, whereby the values of the pre-corroded specimens tend to lead to higher residual fatigue strengths. This can be justified by the superimposed damage mechanisms (e.g., hydrogen embrittlement) during corrosion fatigue loading [15], which are not present under singular mechanical loading after pre-corrosion. Due to the changed degradation mechanism of the PEO-modified variant using GSP, only the substrate material is considered hereafter. The relationship between the immersion time and the (corrosion) fatigue strength can be described by a straight line. By extrapolating, it becomes clear that by applying the short-time testing method, lower corrosion fatigue strength is achieved. In this case, the increased corrosion pit formation lowers the corrosion fatigue strength from 56 MPa (mathematically determined) to 35 MPa.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the impact of galvanostatic polarisation on hydrogen evolution rate, corrosion morphology, residual fatigue strength, and corrosion fatigue strength was investigated using the Mg alloy WE43 with and without a plasma electrolytic oxidation (PEO) layer. The primary objective was to replicate the long-time corrosion behaviour and to assess the mechanical stability of Mg-based implants as they undergo increasing degradation, all within a time-efficient framework. Based on the findings, the following conclusions can be drawn:

By using the short-time testing method, it is possible to reproduce the hydrogen gas evolution and, thus, the corrosion rates. Due to the increased standard potentials of the intermetallic precipitates,

which are arranged parallel in the extrusion direction, an increased corrosion pit formation occurs under polarisation. This can be observed for both material variants so that for the PEO-modified variant, the corrosion mechanism changes, whereas for the substrate material WE43, there is only an amplification of the mechanism that is present anyway. This leads to a drastic decrease in the residual fatigue strength in multiple amplitude tests as well as in the corrosion fatigue strength in constant amplitude tests between the testing conditions at open circuit potential and under galvanostatic polarisation. However, for the PEO-modified specimens, the indicated shift in the corrosion mechanism renders the method unsuitable for predicting long-time degradation behaviour. On the other hand, due to the intensification of the pre-existing mechanism for the substrate material WE43, the method can be used as a worst-case estimation, aiding in the exclusion of unsuitable Mg alloys before advancing to subsequent preclinical studies.

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